

Autonomous RISs and Oblivious Base Stations: The Observer Effect and its Mitigation

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Abstract—Autonomous reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) offer the potential to simplify deployment by reducing the need for real-time remote control between a base station (BS) and an RIS. However, we highlight two major challenges posed by *autonomy*. The first is *implementation complexity*, as autonomy requires hybrid RISs (HRISs) equipped with additional onboard hardware to monitor the propagation environment and perform local channel estimation (CHEST), a process known as probing. The second challenge, termed *probe distortion*, reflects a form of the observer effect: during probing, an HRIS can inadvertently alter the propagation environment, potentially disrupting the operations of other communicating devices sharing the environment. Although implementation complexity has been extensively studied, probe distortion remains largely unexplored. To further assess the potential of autonomous RISs, this paper comprehensively and pragmatically studies the fundamental trade-offs posed by these challenges collectively. In particular, we examine the *robustness* of an HRIS-assisted massive multiple-input multiple-output (mMIMO) system by considering its critical components and stringent conditions. The latter include: (a) two extremes of implementation complexity, represented by minimalist operation designs of two distinct HRIS hardware architectures, and (b) an *oblivious* BS that fully embraces probe distortion. To make our analysis possible, we propose a *physical-layer orchestration framework* that aligns HRIS and mMIMO operations. We present empirical evidence that autonomous RISs remain promising under stringent conditions and outline research directions to deepen probe distortion understanding.

Index Terms—Reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS), intelligent reflective surface (IRS), hybrid reconfigurable intelligent surface (HRIS), massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO).

I. INTRODUCTION

RECONFIGURABLE intelligent surfaces (RISs) are an emerging technology with a significant role on the research agenda toward the 6G [1]–[3]. An RIS consists of a grid of programmable elements that can dynamically control the reflection properties of incoming electromagnetic waves by adjusting the phase shifts of individual elements, collectively termed as a *configuration* [1]. This technology envisions smart radio environments where multiple RISs are deployed to possibly offer benefits such as enhanced spectral efficiency

Fig. 1: Open system models of autonomous RISs allow multiple HRISs to enhance communication performance between BSs and UEs without dedicated and explicit control.

(SE) and reduced electromagnetic-field exposure [2], [4]. In this regard, most research has focused on *nearly-passive* or *solely-reflective* RISs, which possess minimal hardware for element configuration and external communication [1]–[4]. Systems assisted by nearly-passive RISs often operate within a centralized, *non-autonomous* framework, where the RISs are typically controlled by base stations (BSs) via *dedicated* control channels and *explicit* control signaling. This framework heavily relies on end-to-end channel estimation (CHEST) protocols to optimize RIS operations [5]. Thus, achieving efficient real-time remote control poses a significant challenge to their practical implementation [6], [7]. Especially, [8]–[10] show that establishing and designing dedicated, explicit control can be detrimental to communication performance, leading to reduced SE gains and increased latencies. Notably, control costs arise from the allocation of physical resources, such as bandwidth and infrastructure, and engineering requirements that introduce control overhead and reliability issues. Control design also adds unnecessary complexity by requiring simultaneous consideration of multiple factors. These issues underscore a common oversight in prior studies, which often downplayed control-related costs and errors by indiscriminately assuming *ideal control* conditions [1]–[4].

To obviate the need for real-time remote control, recent works focused on studying decentralized frameworks with *autonomous* RISs, which operate independently of BSs while bypassing dedicated and explicit control [11]. This marks a paradigm shift from the traditional hierarchical BS-RIS control to *open* RIS-assisted system models, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Inspired by the potentials of this alternative and the current uncertainty surrounding its feasibility [12]–[16], this paper aims to comprehensively and pragmatically examine the fundamental trade-offs in designing and deploying sys-

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tems assisted by autonomous RISs, focusing on two critical challenges: *implementation complexity* and *probe distortion*. To the best of our knowledge, this paper is the first to address both major challenges within a unified framework. Henceforth, we use the term “autonomous RIS” to refer to the underlying technology and “hybrid RIS (HRIS)” for the hardware that implements it. Conversely, “non-autonomous RIS” denotes the standard “controlled RIS” setup, where a BS manages a nearly-passive RIS via dedicated, explicit control.

A. The Two Major Challenges Posed by Autonomy

1. Implementation complexity: From a hardware perspective, autonomy relies on HRISs equipped with additional onboard hardware to monitor the propagation environment and perform local CHEST, potentially increasing design complexity and associated costs per device. The term “hybrid” highlights their non-passive nature, allowing them to sense by simultaneously absorbing and reflecting incoming waves while lacking the capability to transmit signals; thus, positioning them between nearly-passive RISs and relays [6], [11], [17]. Pioneering hardware solutions for HRISs are presented in [12]–[16], including additional components such as radio-frequency (RF) chains and computing capabilities to execute digital signal processing (DSP) methods. Notably, these works indicate that a minimal HRIS implementation must alternate between **two operation modes**. *i) Probe mode:* The HRIS actively probes the environment to detect the BSs and users’ equipment (UEs), followed by a local CHEST procedure of their channel state information (CSI). The term “probe” highlights the HRIS’ active interaction with the propagation environment, distinguishing it from “sense,” which would suggest a more passive approach. *ii) Reflection mode:* Leveraging the probing knowledge, the HRIS autonomously self-configures to assist ongoing communication performance.

We consider two HRIS hardware architectures from [11]: a low-complexity “power detector (PD)-enabled” and a more complex “DSP-enabled” counterpart. These represent two extremes of implementation complexity concerning DSP power. We design their respective probe and reflection modes to leverage their strengths while being mindful of their weaknesses. Notably, the aforementioned designs remain *minimal* (strict), focusing on essential mathematical analysis rather than the ultimate optimization of HRIS operations. Though not explicitly analyzed, minimal designs also promote low latencies in HRIS operation, a highly desired feature.

2. Probe distortion: We note that autonomous RISs can introduce a form of the *observer effect*, a fundamental concept in physics stating that the act of observation inherently disturbs the observed system. In our context, the HRIS’ probing actions can alter the channel state, potentially disrupting the operations of other communicating devices sharing the environment. We term this disruption as *probe distortion*, where “distortion” is defined as any alteration that modifies a signal’s original shape or characteristics, without specifying whether the impact on communication performance is *unfavorable* or *favorable*. To our knowledge, this effect has often been overlooked in the literature, which arises primarily because current technology

prevents the HRIS from dynamically and seamlessly switching between fully absorbing and fully reflecting incoming waves [12]–[16]. *In essence, the higher the desired probing performance, the higher the level of probing distortion.*

Of particular importance, if unfavorable, probe distortion can be addressed in two main ways, depending on the BS’ awareness of the HRIS—where the BS often acts as the network coordinator [2]. a) *Informed BS:* The BS is fully or partly aware of the HRIS operation. Thus, the BS can mitigate probe distortion by, for example, adopting a *stop-and-wait* strategy, pausing its operation until probing concludes. This option incurs higher overhead, requiring the HRIS to share information about its operation with the BS, or for the BS to actively monitor the environment to discern whether disturbances are due to the HRIS or other causes, potentially wasting resources. Additionally, this information may need to be continuously updated due to the possible adaptive nature of the probe mode and the dynamics of the propagation environment. b) *Oblivious BS:* The BS is completely unaware of the HRIS operation and executes its tasks carelessly.

We argue that considering an informed BS presents a *chicken-and-egg dilemma*, as the primary goal of autonomy is to minimize—*ideally eliminate*—the need for dedicated, explicit control, much like the oblivious BS scenario. The former also introduces higher complexity in network design and operational management, leading to higher resource consumption. Hence, we consider an oblivious BS scenario—a highly stringent condition where the BS fully embraces probe distortion, with no dedicated, explicit control over the HRIS. While this scenario may not represent a definitive practical implementation, analyzing it is essential for risk assessment, providing insights into the consequences of completely lacking control upon a RIS, with significant academic and industrial implications. From an industrial point-of-view, an oblivious BS means that no changes in a currently deployed BS are needed to deploy an HRIS. While our discussion focuses on the BS’ awareness, note that UEs can also experience probe distortion—being its proper evaluation beyond our scope. For example, in carrier-sensing random access [18], [19], UEs evaluate their channel qualities, which may be impacted by probe distortion, making them more likely to be “oblivious” due to their resource scarcity.

B. Why Do We Need a PHY-Layer Orchestration Framework?

Building on the 5G standard [20], we consider an HRIS assisting a massive multiple-input multiple-output (mMIMO) system with an oblivious BS. Typically, an mMIMO system works in time-division duplex (TDD) mode to limit the CSI acquisition overhead [21]. This mode organizes the time-frequency resources in *coherence blocks*, within which the channel remains time-invariant and frequency-flat. Each coherence block ranges from hundreds to several thousands of complex-valued samples, or *samples* for short, depending on the physical characteristics of the propagation environment. The TDD mode sequentially divides each coherence block into **two operation phases** [21]. 1) *CHEST phase:* The UEs transmit uplink (UL) pilot signals, or *pilots* for short, to enable

the BS to perform CHEST and obtain *instantaneous* CSI. We often omit the UL prefix from pilot-related quantities when it is clear from context. Due to channel reciprocity, the estimated CSI at the BS side applies to both downlink (DL) and UL directions. 2) *Communication (COMM) phase*: By using the estimated CSI, the BS can compute *spatial multiplexing* techniques (transmit precoding and receiver combining schemes). For simplicity, we assume that these computations do not incur any overhead. This phase comprises the transmission of DL and UL payload data while the BS spatially separates the UEs.

While the system operates through these phases within a given coherence block, the HRIS must autonomously alternate between its two operation modes. This is where a physical (PHY)-layer orchestration framework comes into play. Such a framework must outline: (a) how the HRIS operation modes are aligned with the simultaneous mMIMO operation phases; and (b) how an intelligent controller acting upon the HRIS can assess the operation modes. To simplify the discussion, we often omit mentioning HRIS and mMIMO about operation modes and phases, respectively, as the word “mode” always refers to HRIS and “phase” to mMIMO.

C. Contributions

Our initial contribution is a PHY-layer orchestration framework, which builds the foundation for comprehensively and pragmatically investigating the following trade-offs concerning the above-stated autonomy challenges.

(1) *Implementation complexity trade-off*: We aim to understand how the overall HRIS performance correlates with the two implementation complexity extremes, characterized by the PD- and DSP-enabled hardware architectures. Here, “overall” refers to both probing and reflecting performance. We also note that each hardware architecture operates differently, resulting in probe distortion with distinct characteristics.

(2) *Autonomous RIS trade-off*: We aim to evaluate the effects of both implementation complexity and probe distortion on the communication performance of an mMIMO system. Specifically, probe distortion gives rise to the *autonomy paradox*, which suggests that the communication performance of an HRIS-assisted mMIMO system can be worse than that of an equivalent, *standalone* mMIMO system. This can occur because probe distortion can hinder spatial multiplexing at an oblivious BS, as it relies on CSI affected by the probing distortion; while efforts to mitigate probe distortion can reduce reflecting performance, as the reflecting performance is inherently linked to the probing one (the output of the probe mode is the input of reflect mode, forming a cascaded system). Thus, our goal is to assess whether probe distortion is *unfavorable* to communication performance. We refer to instances where HRIS-assisted communication performance exceeds that of a standalone mMIMO as the *robust feasibility region*.

We stress that our aim is *not* to provide ultimate optimal design choices; rather, through minimalist designs and the consequent simplified mathematical analysis, we seek to comprehensively and pragmatically uncover the fundamental scaling rules of these trade-offs. Notably, we highlight that the degree of implementation complexity will be controlled

by changing between the two hardware architectures. And, the level of probe distortion can be managed by adjusting the (relative) duration of the probe mode, and it also varies according to the hardware architecture.

Our numerical simulations show that HRIS-assisted communication performance can outperform the standalone performance for a typical suburban setting with UEs in cell-edge conditions. Intriguingly, probe distortion is observed to be *dual* in the ability to be favorable or unfavorable to communication performance. This provides empirical evidence that autonomous RISs can be a promising alternative for practical RISs deployment, even under the considered stringent conditions; most impressively, completely lacking any form of dedicated and explicit control.

D. Paper Outline

Section II reviews related work, while Section III outlines the HRIS-assisted mMIMO system model. In Section IV, we introduce our orchestration framework. Section V and VI detail the HRIS operation modes and the mMIMO operation phases, respectively. Experiments and discussion are provided in Section VII, followed by the conclusions in Section VIII.

E. Notation

Vectors and matrices are in bold lowercase and uppercase letters, respectively. The i, j -th element of a matrix \mathbf{X} is $[\mathbf{X}]_{i,j}$; the i -th element of a vector \mathbf{y} is y_i . The identity matrix of size N is denoted as \mathbf{I}_N while the vector or matrix of zeroes is $\mathbf{0}$, whose dimensions are specified by the context. Complex conjugate, transpose, Hermitian transpose, and diagonal matrix operators are denoted as $(\cdot)^*$, $(\cdot)^\top$, $(\cdot)^H$, and $\text{diag}(\cdot)$, respectively. The ℓ_2 -norm is denoted as $\|\cdot\|_2$, and, when convenient, the inner product between \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} is $\langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \rangle$ while \circ denotes the Hadamard product. Integer sets are represented by calligraphic letters, e.g., \mathcal{A} with cardinality $|\mathcal{A}| = A$, whereas \mathbb{N} , \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{C} denote the sets of natural, real, and complex numbers, respectively. The operators $\Re(\cdot)$ and $\Im(\cdot)$ respectively return the real and the imaginary part of a number. The conditional probability distribution function (PDF) is given by $p(x; E)$, for a random variable x given an event E . The exponential distribution with parameter ζ is $\text{Exp}(\zeta)$. The right-tail distribution of a central χ_n^2 -distributed random variable x with n degrees of freedom is $Q_{\chi_n^2}(x)$ while $Q_{\chi_n^2(\mu)}(x)$ represents a non-central one with non-centrality parameter μ . The complex Gaussian distribution with mean μ and variance σ^2 is denoted as $\mathcal{CN}(\mu, \sigma^2)$. We use $O(\cdot)$ for big-O notation. For clarity, we use the word “channel” to refer to channel vectors or matrices of channel responses. Other less frequent notations are clarified when needed.

II. RELATED WORK

Despite improvements in communication performance and innovative applications [22]–[26], RISs present significant challenges mainly related to their integration into network architecture, such as the execution of end-to-end CHEST [2]–[4]. Methods to integrate non-autonomous RISs into the network

architecture have been introduced in the literature over the last few years; *e.g.*, [27] proposes a software-defined network approach, while [28] exploits machine learning in a similar setting. Technical challenges are further discussed in [29], [30]. Notably, initial standardization efforts are underway to incorporate RISs into 6G standards [31], [32], requesting further validations. While autonomous RISs may reduce the need for network integration, our work focuses primarily on PHY-layer aspects and does not specifically address this issue.

The passive nature of non-autonomous RISs complicates the end-to-end CHEST process [2], [3], [33]. This is further worsened by the large number of RIS elements, which increases the complexity of CHEST and raises control overhead, eventually reducing the quality of the acquired CSI; that is, unfavorably leading to imperfect and/or outdated CSI [34]. Several distinct CHEST procedures have been proposed for non-autonomous RIS-assisted systems [35]–[38]. In [39]–[41], the performance of RIS-assisted mMIMO systems is analyzed under imperfect CSI, examining various precoding and combining techniques, as well as methods for optimizing RIS configurations using either instantaneous or statistical CSI. In [42], the authors study the case of mobile UEs with outdated CSI. *However, in all these works, it is assumed that the BS controls the RIS with negligible overhead and idealized precision.* This assumption is overoptimistic since it overlooks the challenges of designing a dedicated control channel and its potentially harmful effects on communication performance, as shown in [8]–[10].

Autonomous RISs partially address the end-to-end CHEST issue by redistributing the CHEST tasks between the BS and the HRIS. This approach imposes additional costs on the HRIS to reliably receive and process signals for local CHEST [13], yet it shows significant potential, as motivated by [14]–[16], [43], leading to studies on local CHEST procedures. For example, [44] employs a compressive sensing approach for local CHEST relying only on a subset of HRIS elements, while [45] exploits UL pilots for local CHEST. However, their focus is on enhancing local CSI quality, overlooking other aspects. The closest works to ours are [15], [16], [46], in which the HRIS self-optimizes to assist ongoing communication. However, these works only consider the COMM phase assuming prior CSI knowledge, overlooking the effects of probe distortion. Our work provides a more comprehensive analysis encompassing both CHEST and COMM aspects.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider a single-cell mMIMO system where an oblivious BS equipped with a uniform linear array (ULA) of M antennas simultaneously serving K single-antenna UEs that are already scheduled, often referred to as *scheduled UEs* if the context demands.¹ We denote as $K_{\max} \geq K$ the maximum number of UEs that can be supported by the system. Based on the

¹Scheduling UEs in the presence of an HRIS is related to the RIS-assisted initial access problem [18], [19], and it is out of the scope of this paper. However, during scheduling, we ensure that UEs have strong enough channels to the BS so they can still be spatially separable. If UEs were served only with the assistance of the HRIS, spatial separability would be compromised since the channels become linearly dependent. This issue is a well-known problem in RIS-assisted mMIMO systems, *e.g.*, see [39]–[41].

Plug&Play approach from [15], [16], an HRIS is deployed to autonomously enhance the propagation conditions. The HRIS is comprised of $N = N_x N_z$ elements that are arranged as a uniform planar array (UPA), where N_x and N_z denote the number of elements along the x - and z -axis, respectively. We introduce the sets \mathcal{M} , \mathcal{K} , and \mathcal{N} to index BS antennas, UEs, and HRIS elements, respectively. The time-frequency domain is sliced into coherence blocks of τ_c samples, indexed by the set \mathcal{T}_c , where narrow-band wireless transmissions occur at a carrier frequency f_c with wavelength λ and bandwidth B . Fig. 2 provides a geometric representation of the system.

A. Basic HRIS Operation

The HRIS has the sensing capability to both absorb and reflect the incoming waves simultaneously. This can be realized through the use of directional couplers [13], [14], whose *coupling parameter* $\eta \in [0, 1]$ dictates the *fixed* fraction of the received power from an incoming wave that is reflected into the environment; thus, the *fraction of power absorbed* by the HRIS is $1 - \eta$.² The HRIS can alter the propagation environment by changing its configuration. Let $\Theta = \text{diag}([e^{j\theta_1}, \dots, e^{j\theta_N}]^T)$ be a configuration with $\theta_n \in [0, 2\pi]$ denoting the phase-shift impressed by the n -th element. Due to directional couplers, both reflected and absorbed fractions are subject to Θ . Thus, the equivalent BS-UE channel for the k -th UE, $\mathbf{h}_k \in \mathbb{C}^M$, is

$$\mathbf{h}_k(\Theta) = \mathbf{h}_{\text{DR},k} + \mathbf{h}_{\text{RR},k}(\Theta), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_{\text{DR},k} \in \mathbb{C}^M$ is the **direct** channel and $\mathbf{h}_{\text{RR},k} \in \mathbb{C}^M$ is the **reflected** channel, for $k \in \mathcal{K}$. Note that the reflected channel, $\mathbf{h}_{\text{RR},k}$, and the equivalent channel, \mathbf{h}_k , are functions of the configuration, Θ , and can be written in terms of the HRIS-UE channel, $\mathbf{r}_k \in \mathbb{C}^N$, and the BS-HRIS channel, $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N}$. Below, we define the concept of a subblock to help us define how the HRIS operates.

Definition 1 (Subblock). *We let a subblock be a group of samples within the same coherence block. We denote as $\mathcal{T} \subseteq \mathcal{T}_c$ a subblock. Subblocks are indexed by s , which takes values from an index set \mathcal{S} that indexes partitions of samples of size $|\mathcal{T}|$ from \mathcal{T}_c . In the special case that a subblock comprises a single sample, we have $s \in \mathcal{T}_c$ since $|\mathcal{T}| = 1$.*

Assumption 1 (HRIS configuration change). *We assume that the HRIS can change its configuration Θ on a subblock basis. We denote as $\Theta[s]$ the configuration impressed by the HRIS at the s -th subblock, for $s \in \mathcal{S}$.*

The above assumption aligns with the current technology [13], [14]. Indeed, an HRIS requires a time ranging from microseconds to milliseconds to change its configuration [47], whose exact value depends on how the HRIS is built and might correspond to the duration of some samples [9]. As a consequence of this assumption, the equivalent channel also changes on a subblock basis and eq. (1) can be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{h}_k[s] = \mathbf{h}_{\text{DR},k} + \mathbf{h}_{\text{RR},k}[s], \quad (2)$$

²We stress that, with the current technology [14], the coupling parameter η is set by the HRIS hardware design and cannot be tuned dynamically after deployment; but it can be engineered during manufacturing to meet specific requirements of the propagation environment and intended applications.

Fig. 2: Geometric representation of the HRIS-assisted mMIMO system, illustrating the BS, HRIS, and UE, with channel notation defined for the UL direction.

where $\mathbf{h}_{DR,k}$ is not affected by the configuration change. As explained in Section I-A, the HRIS transitions between two operation modes. We will consider that in each mode the HRIS uses different configurations Θ , which are further specified in Section V. This results in distinct equivalent channels, referred to as the *probing equivalent channel* in probe mode, denoted as $\mathbf{h}_{P,k} \in \mathbb{C}^M$, and the *reflecting equivalent channel* in reflection mode, denoted as $\mathbf{h}_{R,k} \in \mathbb{C}^M$, for $k \in \mathcal{K}$.

B. Channel Models

We assume a block-fading model [21]. To simplify, we consider a single UE $k \in \mathcal{K}$, a single coherence block, and, we also get rid of the $[s]$ notation in this subsection. Denote as $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{e} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, and $\mathbf{u}_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$ the locations of the BS center, the HRIS center, and the k -th UE, respectively. The position of the m -th BS antenna is $\mathbf{b}_m \in \mathbb{R}^3$, for $m \in \mathcal{M}$, while of the n -th HRIS element is $\mathbf{e}_n \in \mathbb{R}^3$, for $n \in \mathcal{N}$. The inter-antenna and inter-element distances are set to $\lambda/2$. Let $\mathbf{a}_B(\mathbf{p}) \in \mathbb{C}^M$ and $\mathbf{a}_H(\mathbf{p}) \in \mathbb{C}^N$ denote the respective BS' and HRIS' array response vectors toward a generic location $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$. The n -th element of $\mathbf{a}_H(\mathbf{p})$ is [15]

$$[\mathbf{a}_H(\mathbf{p})]_n = e^{j(\mathbf{k}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{e}), (\mathbf{e}_n - \mathbf{e}))}, \text{ with } \mathbf{k}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{e}) = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \frac{\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{e}}{\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{e}\|_2} \quad (3)$$

being the wave vector; the vector $\mathbf{a}_B(\mathbf{p})$ is derived similarly with \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{b}_m instead of \mathbf{e}, \mathbf{e}_n , respectively. Next, the pathloss model between two generic locations $\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is [15]: $\gamma(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}) = \gamma_0(d_0/\|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q}\|_2)^\beta$, where γ_0 is the channel power gain at a reference distance d_0 and β is the pathloss exponent. In particular, we assume that the direct BS-UEs channels are under a pathloss exponent of β_B , while the BS-HRIS and HRIS-UE are subject to β_H . This assumption is reasonable, as the HRIS is typically positioned to provide clearer propagation paths to the BS and UEs, with fewer obstructions compared to the BS-UEs paths [48].

We assume an independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) Rician fading model for the BS-UE channel, $\mathbf{h}_{DR,k}$, and for the HRIS-UE channel, \mathbf{r}_k , while the BS-HRIS channel, \mathbf{G} , is line-of-sight (LoS) dominant, and hence deterministic. The latter is valid if the HRIS is deployed to have a strong LoS toward the BS, which is often the case due to the flexibility of deployment of the HRIS [48]. However, no such assumption is made on the links between the BS/HRIS and UEs, *e.g.*, due to faster dynamics [21]. Thus, we have

$$\mathbf{h}_{DR,k} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{DR,k}, \sigma_{DR}^2 \mathbf{I}_M) \text{ and } \mathbf{r}_k \sim \mathcal{CN}(\bar{\mathbf{r}}_k, \sigma_{RR}^2 \mathbf{I}_N), \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{DR,k}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_k$ are the LoS components, while σ_{DR}^2 and σ_{RR}^2 are the relative powers of the non-line-of-sight (NLoS) components for the BS-UE and HRIS-UE channels,

Fig. 3: Temporal evolution of the proposed PHY-layer orchestration framework within a coherence block. The mMIMO system alternates between two operation phases: 1) channel estimation (CHEST) and 2) communication (COMM); while the HRIS autonomously alternates between two operation modes: *i*) probe and *ii*) reflection.

respectively. Based on the above, the LoS components are $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{DR,k} = \sqrt{\gamma}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{u}_k) \mathbf{a}_B(\mathbf{u}_k)$, $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_k = \sqrt{\gamma}(\mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{e}) \mathbf{a}_H(\mathbf{e})$, and $\mathbf{G} = \sqrt{\gamma}(\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{e}) \mathbf{a}_B(\mathbf{e}) \mathbf{a}_H^H(\mathbf{b})$. Accordingly, the reflected channel is

$$\mathbf{h}_{RR,k} = (\sqrt{\eta} \mathbf{G} \Theta \mathbf{r}_k) \sim \mathcal{CN}(\sqrt{\eta} \mathbf{G} \Theta \bar{\mathbf{r}}_k, \eta \gamma (\mathbf{b}, \mathbf{e}) N \sigma_{RR}^2 \mathbf{Q}), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{a}_B(\mathbf{e}) \mathbf{a}_B(\mathbf{e})^H$ is a covariance matrix with ones in the diagonal and off-diagonal elements capturing the BS antenna correlation evaluated at the HRIS center. The equivalent BS-UE channel can be obtained by substituting eq. (5) into (2).

IV. A PHY-LAYER ORCHESTRATION FRAMEWORK

In this section, we present our PHY-layer orchestration framework. We begin by introducing two design rules that underpin the framework, illustrated in Fig. 3. Then, we provide a detailed presentation of the proposed framework, including the basic mathematical notation and underlying assumptions.

A. The Two Design Rules

As motivated in Section I, we consider an HRIS-assisted mMIMO system with an oblivious BS, completely lacking dedicated and explicit control between the BS and HRIS. On this basis, we allow for *minimal and implicit* control information exchange between the BS and the HRIS over *existing* control channels. Specifically, the HRIS can listen to standardized control channels—such as the physical downlink control channel (PDCCH) [20]—to acquire synchronization and data frame details, allowing it to align its operation modes to the BS' CHEST and COMM operation phases, similarly to a standard UE. To effectively benefit from the HRIS deployment, we propose an orchestration framework that pragmatically arranges the concurrent operation modes and phases within a coherence block at the PHY layer. This framework is structured around *two design rules*, illustrated in Fig. 3 and detailed below.

First design rule: *The probe mode must take place during the CHEST phase.* This is a natural choice that enables the HRIS to leverage UL pilots for identifying scheduled UEs and locally estimating their CSI, as in [45]. Effectively, the HRIS can exploit the channel reciprocity inherent from TDD

operation and, consequently, it can estimate the local CSI in the UL direction only and extrapolate it to the DL.³ The big downside of this design rule is that probing can alter the channel state during the CHEST phase (observer effect), hence distorting the CSI estimated by the BS. As mentioned, we name this effect as probe distortion. *Therefore, probe distortion manifests as a distortion introduced by the HRIS into the estimated CSI at the BS.* This results in an imperfect, probe-distorted CSI at the BS, which can adversely affect the spatial separation of UEs during the COMM phase, potentially degrading communication performance.

Second design rule: *The reflection mode must take place before the end of the CHEST phase and during the entire COMM phase.* This approach attempts to address a key limitation of autonomous RISs, which challenges a foundational principle of the mMIMO technology: the assumption that CSI estimated during the CHEST phase remains consistent with the channel state during the COMM phase [21]. To exemplify this, Fig. 4 illustrates the evolution of the power of an equivalent UL BS-UE channel, as defined in (2), over a coherence block, reproducing the HRIS' switching between its operation modes. Distinct channel state characteristics are observed: during probe mode, the *probing equivalent channels* can vary as the HRIS can alter its configuration to probe for UEs. In contrast, during reflection mode, the *reflecting equivalent channel* is *stable* since the HRIS loads and maintains a fixed reflection configuration after finishing probing, which is kept until the next coherence block begins. We assume that the computation of configurations does not incur any overhead. By imposing the start of the reflection mode to occur during the CHEST phase, we aim to enable the BS to collect enough samples of the reflecting equivalent channel, but on the effect of probe distortion, attempting to ensure adequate spatial separation of the UEs during the COMM phase.⁴

B. Detailed Description

Figure 5 illustrates how the coherence block is sliced simultaneously into the different operation phases and modes. We let τ_{chest} and τ_{comm} be the number of samples comprising the CHEST and COMM phases, respectively, such that $\tau_c = \tau_{\text{chest}} + \tau_{\text{comm}}$. The COMM phase can be further divided into τ_d and τ_u samples for DL and UL data traffic, respectively; that is, $\tau_{\text{comm}} = \tau_d + \tau_u$. Simultaneously, we let $\tau_{\text{prob}} \leq \tau_{\text{chest}}$ and τ_{refl} be the number of samples comprising the probe and reflection modes, respectively, with $\tau_c = \tau_{\text{prob}} + \tau_{\text{refl}}$.

We now outline the basic execution of the CHEST phase via UL pilot signaling [21]. During connection establishment within a given coherence block, the BS performs a pilot assignment $p(i) : \mathcal{K} \mapsto \mathcal{T}_p$, where each scheduled UE is deterministically assigned a pilot from a total of τ_p pilots,

³We assume channel reciprocity is perfectly achieved, e.g., by using carefully designed hardware and calibration algorithms [21], allowing us to focus on discussing our main ideas. Future research could explore what happens if channel reciprocity is violated by/at the HRIS.

⁴The design choices we made form *one possible* orchestration framework. Alternative frameworks could be proposed, but we argue that our choices are both natural and well-aligned with mMIMO technology, providing a basic platform to analyze the relevant trade-offs outlined in Section I-C.

Fig. 4: Example of the evolution of the equivalent UL BS-UE channel gain, $\mathbf{h}_k[s]$ in (2), over a coherence block of 32 subblocks with the HRIS changing its configuration every subblock. During the probe mode, the channel state of the *probing equivalent channels* can vary significantly whereas the *reflecting equivalent channel* remains stable during the reflection mode. The oblivious BS attempts to estimate the reflecting equivalent channel while the HRIS is probing; as a result, *probe distortion* can degrade the quality of the CSI at the BS.

indexed by the set $\mathcal{T}_p \subset \mathcal{T}_c$ with $|\mathcal{T}_p| = \tau_p$, for $i \in \mathcal{K}$. In other words, $p(i) \in \mathcal{T}_p$ represents the index of the pilot assigned to UE i . We say a pilot is *active* if it is assigned to a UE; otherwise, it is *inactive*. Note that at most only one UE can be associated with each pilot. Each pilot $\Phi_t \in \mathbb{R}^{\tau_p}$ spans for τ_p samples, for $t \in \mathcal{T}_p$. The pilots are selected from a *pilot codebook* $\Phi \in \mathbb{R}^{\tau_p \times \tau_p}$. To avoid interference and simplify the analysis, we assume the following about the pilot codebook.

Assumption 2 (Orthogonal UL pilot codebook). *The pilot codebook contains mutually orthogonal pilots, such that $\Phi_t^H \Phi_{t'} = \tau_p$ if $t = t'$ and $\Phi_t^H \Phi_{t'} = 0$ if $t \neq t'$, $\forall t, t' \in \mathcal{T}_p$. In particular, we assume $\Phi = \sqrt{\tau_p} \mathbf{I}_{\tau_p}$ and that the maximum number of UEs is equal to the pilot length, i.e., $K_{\text{max}} = \tau_p$.*

The above is based on the rule of thumb described in [21] for selecting the number of pilots without interference. We further assume that the HRIS knows Φ and, hence, τ_p and K_{max} , e.g., by listening to the PDCCCH [20]. Due to our design rules and orthogonality, an issue emerges if the duration of the CHEST phase is equal to the pilot length, that is, $\tau_{\text{chest}} = \tau_p$. To see it, consider the following example.

Example 1. *Consider that $K = K_{\text{max}} = \tau_p = 2$ and that $\tau_{\text{chest}} = \tau_p$. Assume that UE-1 is assigned to the UL pilot $[\sqrt{2}, 0]^T$ and UE-2 to $[0, \sqrt{2}]^T$. Based on our framework, we want $0 < \tau_{\text{prob}} < \tau_{\text{chest}}$; hence, we choose $\tau_{\text{prob}} = 1$. In this case, the HRIS would receive just the first entries of the pilots. Since the first entry of UE-2's pilot is 0, the HRIS would be able to probe only UE-1, no matter what UE-2 does.*

To solve the above problem, we assume the following *pilot repetition strategy*, consequently defining the duration of the CHEST phase.⁵

Assumption 3 (UL pilot repetition: Duration of the CHEST phase). *Each UE re-transmits its pilot for $L > 1$ times such that $\tau_{\text{chest}} = L\tau_p$. We refer to each of the pilot repetitions as a UL pilot subblock, following Definition 1, which is indexed*

⁵We note that the only explicit modification made in this work to incorporate autonomous RISs into standard mMIMO technology is the repetition of UL pilots. While this does not dictate practical implementation—such as using non-orthogonal pilot codebooks to eliminate the need for repetition—orthogonality simplifies the required designs and the interpretation of relevant trade-offs. End-to-end CHEST procedures with non-autonomous RISs also modify standard mMIMO (e.g., [33]), making our assumption reasonable.

Fig. 5: Sample-based organization of a coherence block.

by the set \mathcal{L} with \mathcal{L} being a partition of the set \mathcal{T}_p . We index variables that occur on a pilot-subblock basis by introducing an $[l]$ in front of it, with $l \in \mathcal{L}$.

This assumption allows us to effectively accommodate the probe mode within the CHEST phase while avoiding the problem seen in Example 1. To enhance clarity, we will omit the prefix term “pilot” from subblocks when the context allows. We now define the duration of the modes as follows.

Definition 2 (Duration of the modes). *The probing duration can be defined as an integer multiple of the pilot length τ_p , satisfying $0 < \tau_{\text{prob}} \leq \tau_{\text{chest}}$. Thus, the probe mode spans for $\tau_{\text{prob}} = C\tau_p$, where $1 \leq C \leq L$ represents the number of pilot subblocks utilized by the HRIS for probing. The specific subblocks during which the HRIS probes are collected in the subset $C \subseteq \mathcal{L}$. To clarify, we introduce a notation $[c]$ to index variables that occur on a pilot subblock basis during probing, with $c \in C$. Hence, the fraction of the coherence block that the HRIS operates in reflection mode is $\tau_{\text{refl}} = \tau_c - C\tau_p$.*

We further define the following relative quantities.

Definition 3 (Relative duration of the modes within the CHEST phase). *The relative duration of the probe mode within the CHEST phase can be defined as:*

$$\varpi = \frac{C}{L}, \text{ with } 0 \leq \varpi \leq 1, \quad (6)$$

where ϖ equals 0 in the absence of the probe mode, $C = 0$, and equals 1 when the probe mode occupies the entire duration of the CHEST phase, $C = L$. Hence, the relative duration of the reflection mode is $1 - \varpi$.

With the orchestration framework and associated notation established, we can proceed to the system design, naturally dividing it into the HRIS and mMIMO components, while remaining mindful of the trade-offs outlined in Section I-C.

V. DESIGNING THE HRIS OPERATION

In this section, we design the HRIS operation with the trade-offs defined in Section I-C in mind. We first introduce the two hardware architectures, followed by the general considerations for the probe mode and two probing strategies tailored to each architecture. For clarity, we avoid overloading notation by not differentiating signals related to each architecture. Next, we outline a common reflection mode for both architectures. Finally, we discuss the computational complexity of the HRIS operation for each architecture.

Fig. 6: PD- and DSP-enabled HRIS hardware architectures.

A. The Two Hardware Architectures

Figure 6 depicts the two HRIS hardware architectures, representing two implementation complexity extremes. They follow the same basic operation from Section III-A, switching between operation modes by using or not the sensing hardware and loading configurations according to each mode. However, they differ in their DSP capabilities, as follows. A PD-enabled HRIS has a single RF-combiner in the absorption branch, which analogically sums the signals absorbed by each element, followed by an RF-power detector. This hardware architecture is the least complex and is limited to processing the combined received power only, that is, a *single digital data stream* [15], [16]. A DSP-enabled HRIS has an RF chain for each element, resulting in N *separated digital data streams*. Thus, more advanced DSP techniques can be applied over the N acquired samples [14].

B. Probe Mode: General Considerations

Building on Section IV, we now discuss general considerations for the probe mode applicable to both hardware architectures. We begin with a simplifying assumption: the BS-HRIS CSI has been perfectly acquired at the HRIS, e.g., by listening to standard synchronization and DL pilot signals periodically transmitted by the BS [20]. This assumption is supported because, following Section III-B, the coherence time of the BS-HRIS channel, \mathbf{G} , is often longer than that of the HRIS-UE channels, given the static nature of both the BS and HRIS [49]. Thus, we do not address the design of this aspect.

On the other hand, we address the design of detecting scheduled UEs followed by a local CHEST procedure of their CSI. From Section IV-B, the UEs transmit UL pilots for L pilot subblocks while the HRIS probes during C out of the L subblocks. For the c -th subblock, the superimposed pilots, defined as $\mathbf{\Pi}[c] \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times \tau_p}$, impinging at the HRIS are

$$\mathbf{\Pi}[c] = \sqrt{\rho} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{r}_i \Phi_{p(i)}^\top, \quad (7)$$

where ρ is the UE transmit power, $p(i)$ denotes the pilot assigned to the i -th UE, and \mathbf{r}_i is the HRIS-UE channel of the i -th UE, as in (4), for $c \in C$.

Per Assumption 1, we establish that the HRIS can change its configuration to help in probing for UEs. For example, the HRIS can “scan” the surrounding area by changing its configurations to detect signals coming from different directions. We refer to these as *probing configurations*. Based on Assumption

2, the HRIS can change probing configurations on a pilot subblock basis. Motivated by [15], [19], we will limit ourselves to the case that a *probing configuration codebook* is available at the HRIS, which is comprised of C configurations—one configuration per pilot subblock—and is denoted as

$$\Theta_P = \{\Theta_P[c] \mid c \in C\}. \quad (8)$$

In general, the HRIS must detect the scheduled UEs and locally estimate their CSI. However, not all scheduled UEs can be served by the HRIS. For instance, a UE located far from the HRIS may be scheduled yet remain undetectable due to factors such as low received power, which may arise from an inadequate probing design or insufficient probing duration.⁶

To design the probe mode, we employ detection and estimation theories [50], [51]. In particular, we adopt two *suboptimal* choices.⁷ The first choice is *channel-agnostic probing*, meaning that the probe mode does not rely on any prior knowledge of channel models, that is, the channels are treated as deterministic signals.⁸ Evidently, probing performance will vary statistically according to channel distributions and related parameters; the latter are treated as known nuisance parameters for performance evaluation [50]. Choosing this approach can also be justified by unfavorable characteristics of the propagation environment and application scenarios; *e.g.*, rapid changes in the behaviors of UEs [21]. The second choice is *minimal probing*, indicating that our aim is to capture essential probing functionalities without disproportionately favoring any specific hardware architecture. This is achieved by considering the simplest detection problem in the context of each hardware architecture: determining whether a signal embedded in noise is present or not [50]. Here, the signal of interest is treated as deterministic, while the noise distribution, although known, is not necessarily Gaussian and may have unknown parameters.

These choices can be interpreted as establishing a lower bound on probing performance for each hardware architecture, thereby offering a *basic platform* for comparing the two architectures. We incentivize the study of more elaborated designs if the computational complexity remains practical.

Output of the probe mode: At the end of the HRIS probing procedure, there are three main outputs that are going to be input to the reflection mode. First, the *set of detected UEs*, denoted as $\mathcal{K}_D \subseteq \mathcal{K}$ with $|\mathcal{K}_D| = K_D$ and $K_D \leq K$. Second, we note that the *local CSI* needed by the HRIS is the angular information of the HRIS-UE channels, $\angle \mathbf{r}_j$, which we denote as $\hat{\Theta}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$, for $j \in \mathcal{K}_D$. Third, a vector of *relative importance weights*, denoted by $\omega = [\omega_1, \dots, \omega_{K_D}]^T \in \mathbb{R}_+^{K_D}$, representing the relevance of each detected UE.⁹

⁶One could argue that the BS can inform the HRIS about scheduled UEs through standard control channels. However, this does not eliminate the need for probing since a core part of it is to identify the relative positions of the UEs at the HRIS. Of course, if the UEs are static and their channels as well (flat-fading), the HRIS could probe less frequently.

⁷We recall that our objective is not to optimize thoroughly the HRIS operation but to comprehensively explore the fundamental trade-offs of an HRIS-assisted system with a focus on robustness, as outlined in Section I.

⁸If partial or complete knowledge of channel models is available, more effective probe designs could be achieved.

⁹As in [15], we focus on designing ω by favoring UEs according to their received amplitudes at the HRIS. Other designs can be explored in the future.

Implementation complexity and probe distortion: We observe that each hardware architecture leads to probe distortion with different characteristics. These differences arise from the specific configurations of the probe codebooks, Θ_P , the design of the probing scheme itself, and the influence of probing performance on reflection performance.

C. PD-Enabled Probe Mode

1) *Design of the probing configuration codebook:* Similar to [15] and to overcome the lack of DSP capabilities, the PD-enabled HRIS probes for UEs by *sweeping* through probing configurations in Θ_P . Thus, we build the probing configuration codebook to slice the 3D space into C uniform sectors of interest, with $C = C_{el}C_{az}$ being decomposed into elevation and azimuth directions, respectively. The n -th diagonal element of the c -th probing configuration is

$$[\Theta_P[c]]_{n,n} = e^{j(\mathbf{k}(\mathbf{p}[c], \mathbf{e}), (\mathbf{e}_n - \mathbf{e}))}, \quad (9)$$

for $n \in \mathcal{N}$ and $c \in C$, where the c -th probed position is $\mathbf{p}[c] = [\sin \psi[c] \cos \phi[c], \sin \psi[c] \cos \phi[c], \cos \psi[c]]^T$, with the respective elevation and azimuth angular directions being $\psi[c] = \pi/C_{el}(\text{mod}_{C_{el}}(c-1) + 1/2)$ and $\phi[c] = \pi/C_{az}((c-1 - \text{mod}_{C_{el}}(c-1))/C_{el} + 1/2)$.

2) *Probing procedure and performance analysis:* Consider a given pilot subblock c in which the c -th probing configuration is loaded at the HRIS according to (9), for $c \in C$. Let $\theta_P[c] \in \mathbb{C}^N$ denote the diagonal elements of $\Theta_P[c]$. Based on (7) and after the RF-combiner (see Fig. 6), the received signal at the c -th subblock, $\mathbf{y}[c] \in \mathbb{C}^{\tau_p}$, is given by

$$(\mathbf{y}[c])^T = \sqrt{1 - \eta} \sqrt{\rho} (\theta_P[c])^H \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{r}_i \Phi_{p(i)}^T \right) + (\mathbf{n}[c])^T, \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{n}[c] = [n_1[c], \dots, n_{\tau_p}[c]]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{\tau_p}$ is the receiver noise at the HRIS after the RF-combiner; the noise is i.i.d. over different subblocks and distributed as $CN(\mathbf{0}, N\sigma_H^2 \mathbf{I}_{\tau_p})$ with σ_H^2 being the *HRIS noise power*. Let us focus on the t -th pilot and the k -th UE, for $t \in \mathcal{T}_p$ and $k \in \mathcal{K}$. Based on Assumption 2, the above expression can be rewritten as

$$y_t[c] = \begin{cases} \sqrt{1 - \eta} \sqrt{\rho} \sqrt{\tau_p} (\theta_P[c])^H \mathbf{r}_k + n_t[c], & \text{if } p(k) = t \\ n_t[c], & \text{o/w.} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Let $\alpha_t[c] = |y_t[c]|^2$ denote the signal after the RF-power detector in Fig. 6. Then, we have that

$$\alpha_t[c] = \begin{cases} |A_k[c]|^2 + 2\Re\{A_k[c]n_t[c]\} + |n_t[c]|^2, & \text{if } p(k) = t \\ |n_t[c]|^2, & \text{o/w,} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where the amplitude A_k is defined as $A_k[c] = \sqrt{1 - \eta} \sqrt{\rho} \sqrt{\tau_p} (\theta_P[c])^H \mathbf{r}_k$. The PD-enabled HRIS can store and digitally process the signals $\alpha_t[c]$, $\forall t \in \mathcal{T}_p$, to detect the UEs. We stress that $y_t[c]$ is not accessible for processing, since the PD-enabled RIS can just measure the combined received power, $\alpha_t[c]$ (see Fig. 6).

Thus, the PD-enabled HRIS detects if the k -th UE is in the direction probed by the c -th configuration by applying

the following binary hypothesis test over each pilot [50]:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}_0^{(k)}[c] : \alpha_t[c] &= |n_t[c]|^2 \implies A_k[c] = 0, \\ \mathcal{H}_1^{(k)}[c] : \alpha_t[c] &= |y_t[c]|^2 \implies A_k[c] \neq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where the null hypothesis denotes the case in which the k -th UE was not assigned to the t -th pilot, that is, $p(k) \neq t$ and, consequently, $A_k[c] = 0$. Note that the test is performed on the amplitude $A_k[c]$, which is not directly observed from $\alpha_t[c]$, as seen in (12). Hence, we need to estimate $A_k[c]$ from $\alpha_t[c]$. Let f_{MLE} denote the maximum-likelihood estimator (MLE). The MLE for $|A_k[c]|^2$ from $\alpha_t[c]$ is $f_{\text{MLE}}(A_k[c]) = \alpha_t[c]$. Thus, the PD-enabled HRIS decides $\mathcal{H}_1^{(k)}[c]$ if [50, p. 200]:

$$\frac{p(\alpha_t[c]; f_{\text{MLE}}(A_k[c]), \mathcal{H}_1^{(k)}[c])}{p(\alpha_t[c]; \mathcal{H}_0^{(k)}[c])} > \epsilon_s, \quad (14)$$

where ϵ_s is a threshold parameter. The detailed test description can be seen in Appendix A, which relies on an approximation based on ignoring the cross-term in (12). We evaluate the approximated performance of the PD-enabled HRIS below.

Corollary 1 (PD-enabled probing performance). *An approximated closed-form expression of the performance of the PD-based probe mode given by the test in (13) can be found in the asymptotic case of $N \rightarrow \infty$ as [50]:*

$$P_{\text{D}}^{(k)}[c] = e^{-\frac{1}{2N\sigma_{\text{H}}^2}(\epsilon_s' - \alpha_t[c])} \quad \text{and} \quad P_{\text{FA}}^{(k)}[c] = e^{-\frac{1}{2N\sigma_{\text{H}}^2}\epsilon_s'}, \quad (15)$$

where $P_{\text{D}}^{(k)}[c]$ and $P_{\text{FA}}^{(k)}[c]$ are the probabilities of detection and false alarm for detecting the k -th UE in the c -th pilot subblock, respectively, for $c \in \mathcal{C}$ and $k \in \mathcal{K}$. The threshold parameter ϵ_s' is proportional to ϵ_s in (14).

Proof. The proof is given in Appendix A. \square

We note that the above performance measures overestimate the real performance due to approximations made. Moreover, the measures are stochastic and vary on a coherence-block basis with factors such as the positions of UEs.

3) *Output:* After performing the test in (13) over all τ_p pilots, the HRIS stores the detected UEs in the set $\mathcal{K}_{\text{D}}[c] = \{k \in \mathcal{K} \mid \mathcal{H}_1^{(k)}[c] \text{ is true}\}$. This is repeated and aggregated over all C pilot subblocks. The HRIS then stores all the detected UEs along with their corresponding probing configurations that achieved the highest received power as:

$$\mathcal{K}_{\text{D}} = \bigcup_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \mathcal{K}_{\text{D}}[c] \quad \text{and} \quad c_j = \arg \max_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \alpha_{p(j)}[c], \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_{\text{D}}. \quad (16)$$

The PD-enabled HRIS cannot explicitly estimate the HRIS-UE channels, \mathbf{r}_j , of the detected UEs since it is limited to observe signal power, as in (12). Therefore, the best this HRIS can do is to use the probing configuration that achieved the highest received power as an estimate of the local CSI for each detected UE. Thus, the local CSI at the PD-enabled HRIS is

$$\hat{\Theta}_j = \Theta_{\text{P}}[c_j], \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_{\text{D}}, \quad (17)$$

where c_j comes from (16) and relative importance weights are

$$\omega_j = \sqrt{\alpha_{p(j)}[c_j]} / \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{K}_{\text{D}}} \sqrt{\alpha_{p(j')}[c_{j'}]}, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_{\text{D}}. \quad (18)$$

For the PD-enabled HRIS, testing on a subblock basis is crucial, as the local CSI estimation relies on this structure.

D. DSP-Enabled Probe Mode

1) *Design of the probing configuration codebook:* A DSP-enabled HRIS can process the received signals coming from all elements simultaneously, and, thus, it can always reverse back the effect of any impressed probing configuration $\Theta_{\text{P}}[c]$ digitally at the price of increased computational effort. This involves multiplying a signal received at a given sample of the c -th pilot subblock by $\Theta_{\text{P}}^{-1}[c]$. Thus, we assume that the probing configuration codebook Θ_{P} is $\Theta_{\text{P}}[c] = \mathbf{I}_N, \forall c \in \mathcal{C}$.

2) *Probing procedure and performance analysis:* Based on (7) and the above Θ_{P} , the received signal at the c -th pilot subblock, $\mathbf{Y}_c \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times \tau_p}$, is given by

$$\mathbf{Y}[c] = \sqrt{1 - \eta} \sqrt{\rho} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{r}_i \Phi_{p(i)}^{\top} + \mathbf{N}[c], \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{N}[c] \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times \tau_p}$ is the receiver noise matrix with columns distributed according to $\mathbf{n}_t[c] \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_{\text{H}}^2 \mathbf{I}_N)$ with noise i.i.d. over subblocks. Unlike the PD-enabled, the DSP-enabled HRIS can process the received signal over the element-dimension, N , the pilot-dimension, τ_p , and the pilot-subblock-dimension, c . We explore this next. Let us focus on the t -th pilot and the k -th UE, for $t \in \mathcal{T}_p$ and $k \in \mathcal{K}$. We start by processing over the pilot dimension. The HRIS de-correlates the received signal with respect to (w.r.t.) the t -th pilot as:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_t[c] = \mathbf{Y}[c] \Phi_t^* = \begin{cases} \sqrt{1 - \eta} \sqrt{\rho} \tau_p \mathbf{r}_k + \tilde{\mathbf{n}}_t[c], & \text{if } p(k) = t \\ \tilde{\mathbf{n}}_t[c], & \text{o/w,} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}_t[c] \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \tau_p \sigma_{\text{H}}^2 \mathbf{I}_N)$. Next, to combat noise, the above signals can be averaged over subblocks as

$$\check{\mathbf{y}}_t = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \tilde{\mathbf{y}}_t[c] = \begin{cases} \sqrt{1 - \eta} \sqrt{\rho} \tau_p \mathbf{r}_k + \check{\mathbf{n}}_t, & \text{if } p(k) = t \\ \check{\mathbf{n}}_t[c], & \text{o/w,} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

where $\check{\mathbf{n}}_{p(k)} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \tau_p \sigma_{\text{H}}^2 / C) \mathbf{I}_N$. Let $\mathbf{s}_t = \sqrt{1 - \eta} \sqrt{\rho} \tau_p \mathbf{r}_k$ be the complex signal observed if the k -th UE transmitted the t -th pilot, that is, $p(k) = t$ and $\mathbf{s}_t = \mathbf{0}$ otherwise. The DSP-enabled HRIS can store and digitally process the signals $\check{\mathbf{y}}_t, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}_p$, to detect the UEs.

Thus, the DSP-enabled HRIS detects the k -th UE by applying the following binary hypothesis test over each pilot [50]:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}_0^{(k)} : \check{\mathbf{y}}_t &= \check{\mathbf{n}}_t \implies \mathbf{s}_t = \mathbf{0}, \\ \mathcal{H}_1^{(k)} : \check{\mathbf{y}}_t &= \mathbf{s}_t + \check{\mathbf{n}}_t \implies \mathbf{s}_t \neq \mathbf{0}, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where, as before, the null hypothesis denotes the case in which the k -th UE was not assigned to the t -th pilot. Unlike the PD-enabled, the detection is now independent on the pilot subblocks due to the higher DSP capability. Thus, the DSP-enabled HRIS decides $\mathcal{H}_1^{(k)}$ if [50, p. 500]:

$$\frac{2C}{\tau_p \sigma_{\text{H}}^2} \|\check{\mathbf{y}}_t\|_2^2 > \epsilon_s, \quad (23)$$

where ϵ_s is a threshold parameter. We evaluate the performance of the DSP-enabled HRIS probe mode below.

Corollary 2 (DSP-enabled probing performance). *A closed-form expression of the performance of the DSP-enabled HRIS probe mode given by the test in (23) can be found as [50]*

$$P_D^{(k)} = \mathcal{Q}_{\chi_{2N}^2}(\mu)(\epsilon_s) \text{ and } P_{FA}^{(k)} = \mathcal{Q}_{\chi_{2N}^2}(\epsilon_s), \quad (24)$$

where $P_D^{(k)}$ and $P_{FA}^{(k)}$ are the probabilities of detection and false alarm for detecting the k -th UE, respectively, and $\mu = 2(1 - \eta)\rho\tau_p \|\mathbf{r}_k\|_2^2 / \sigma_H^2$, for $k \in \mathcal{K}$.

Proof. The proof follows directly from [50, p. 500]. \square

Unlike Corollary 1, the probing performance is now independent of the pilot subblocks. However, it remains stochastic and exhibits variability on a coherence-block basis, influenced by factors such as the positions of the UEs.

3) *Output:* After performing the test in (23) over all τ_p pilots, the HRIS stores the detected UEs in the set $\mathcal{K}_D = \{t | \mathcal{H}_1^{(t)} \text{ is true, } t \in \mathcal{T}_p\}$. Unlike the PD-enabled, the DSP-enabled HRIS can explicitly estimate the angular information of the HRIS-UE channels, $\angle \mathbf{r}_j$, for $j \in \mathcal{K}_D$, by exploiting the signal in (21) to perform such estimation. We now describe such an estimation process for the j -th detect UE assigned to the t -th pilot with $p(j) = t$, for $j \in \mathcal{K}_D$. Let $\boldsymbol{\theta}_j = \angle \mathbf{r}_j \in \mathbb{C}^N$ denote the angular information of the HRIS-UE channel, which we are interested in estimating. From (21), we observe that the angular information contained in \mathbf{s}_i is equivalent to the one contained in \mathbf{r}_j , that is, $\angle \mathbf{s}_i \equiv \angle \mathbf{r}_j$, since \mathbf{s}_i is proportional to \mathbf{r}_j . The estimation of $\boldsymbol{\theta}_j$ is then based on rewriting the signal in (21) as $\check{\mathbf{y}}_t = \mathbf{s}_i + \check{\mathbf{n}}_t$. Thus, the HRIS estimates $\boldsymbol{\theta}_j$ as

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_j = \exp \left(1j \arctan \left(\frac{\Im(\check{\mathbf{y}}_t)}{\Re(\check{\mathbf{y}}_t)} \right) \right), \quad (25)$$

where the $\exp(\cdot)$ and $\arctan(\cdot)$ functions are applied element-wise over the vector entries, and we use the notation $1j$ to stress the difference between the UE index and the imaginary unit. The estimation error can be numerically approximated as the variance of the signal $\check{\mathbf{y}}_t \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{s}_i, (\tau_p \sigma_H^2 / C) \mathbf{I}_N)$. Thus, the local CSI at the DSP-enabled HRIS is

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}_j = \text{diag}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_j), \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_D. \quad (26)$$

Similar to before, we compute the corresponding weights as

$$\omega_j = \|\check{\mathbf{y}}_{p(j)}\|_2 / \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{K}_D} \|\check{\mathbf{y}}_{p(j')}\|_2, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_D. \quad (27)$$

E. Reflection Mode

We design the reflection mode based on the outputs of the probe mode, specifically, the set of detected UEs, \mathcal{K}_D , the local CSI, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}_j$, and the relative importance weights, ω_j , $\forall j \in \mathcal{K}_D$. The latter two quantities are provided in eqs. (17) and (18) for a PD-enabled HRIS, and in eqs. (26) and (27) for a DSP-enabled while the former is the collective result of the tests in (13) and (22), respectively. Thus, the design of the reflection mode remains independent of the HRIS hardware architecture, although its performance eventually differs due to distinct probe performance. In principle, the HRIS would load *one* reflection configuration to assist the UL data traffic and

another for DL. However, by leveraging channel reciprocity, we note that the reflection configuration for the DL is the complex conjugate of the one used during UL. Hence, we focus solely on designing a single reflection configuration for UL, denoted as $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}_R$. In particular, we adopt the reflection design from [15], whose goal is to maximize the received signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the detected UEs while taking into account their relative importance weights. This is obtained by setting $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}_R$ as

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}_R = \boldsymbol{\Theta}_B \circ \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_D} \omega_k \hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}_k^*, \quad (28)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Theta}_B = \text{diag}(\mathbf{a}_H(\mathbf{b}))$ denotes the perfect CSI of the HRIS-BS channel, \mathbf{G} . Similar to probing, we argue that this is a minimal reflecting design (see details in [15]).

Evaluating reflecting performance: We now present a metric to evaluate the designed reflection configuration. In an ideal scenario of perfect probing, the HRIS would employ the following optimal reflection configuration, assuming that all UEs are detected and their CSI is accurately estimated:

$$\boldsymbol{\Theta}_R^* = \boldsymbol{\Theta}_B \circ \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \omega_k^* \text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k^*), \quad (29)$$

where we use $(\cdot)^*$ to denote optimal in the sense defined in [15] with $\boldsymbol{\theta}_k^* = \exp(j \arctan(\Im(\mathbf{r}_k) / \Re(\mathbf{r}_k)))$ and $\omega_k^* = \|\mathbf{r}_k\|_2 / \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \|\mathbf{r}_i\|_2$. Thus, a metric for evaluating reflection accuracy is the normalized mean-squared error (NMSE):

$$\text{NMSE}_H(\varpi) = \|\hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}_R - \boldsymbol{\Theta}_R^*\|_2^2 / \|\boldsymbol{\Theta}_R^*\|_2^2, \quad (30)$$

which is a function of the relative probe duration ϖ (see Def. 3) and where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}_R$ and $\boldsymbol{\Theta}_R^*$ are the respective diagonals of $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}_R$ and $\boldsymbol{\Theta}_R^*$. Observe that $\text{NMSE}_H(\varpi)$ captures implementation complexity, as it depends on the chosen HRIS hardware architecture, and probe distortion, as it depends on probing performance; it also statistically varies over coherence blocks with factors such as the positions of UEs, and channel and noise realizations.

F. Complexity Analysis: HRIS Operation Modes

For the PD-enabled HRIS, the RF-combiner and power detector can be implemented with analog circuitry. Thus, computing is required for (14), (16), and (18), yielding in a total of $C + K_{\max}C + 3K_{\max}$ element-wise operations. The DSP-enabled HRIS performs (20), (21), (23), (25), and (27), resulting in a total of $NK_{\max}^3 + 5NK_{\max} + CN + 2N$ element-wise operations. By adding up $2NK_{\max}$ operations to compute the diagonal reflection configuration in (28), we obtain the computational complexities of $\mathcal{O}(K_{\max}(2N + C + 3) + C)$ for the PD-enabled HRIS and of $\mathcal{O}(N(K_{\max}^3 + 7K_{\max} + C + 2))$ for the DSP-enabled one. Hence, observe that the complexity of the PD-enabled HRIS increases linearly with system parameters while the complexity of the DSP-enabled scales cubically with K_{\max} ; more concerning is the comparison between $2NK_{\max}$ for the former against NK_{\max}^3 for the latter.

VI. DESIGNING THE mMIMO OPERATION

In this section, we adapt the design of a traditional mMIMO system [21] to account for the influence of HRIS operation,

having the trade-offs defined in Section I-C in mind. For generality, we will assume a generic HRIS hardware architecture, interchangeable with either PD-enabled, DSP-enabled, or other architectures. For simplicity, we assume the COMM phase includes only UL traffic, with $\tau_d = 0$ and $\tau_u = \tau_c - L\tau_p$; extension to the DL case is straightforward.

A. CHEST Phase

Based on Sections III and IV, we can now formally define the following two equivalent channels for the i -th UE:

$$\mathbf{h}_{p,i}[l] = \mathbf{h}_{\text{DR},i} + \sqrt{\eta} \mathbf{G} \mathbf{\Theta}_P[l] \mathbf{r}_i \text{ and } \mathbf{h}_{R,i} = \mathbf{h}_{\text{DR},i} + \sqrt{\eta} \mathbf{G} \hat{\mathbf{\Theta}}_R \mathbf{r}_i, \quad (31)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_{p,i}[l]$ denotes the *probing equivalent channel* during the l -th pilot subblock and $\mathbf{h}_{R,i}$ represents the *reflecting equivalent channel*, for $l \in C$ and $i \in \mathcal{K}$. Recall that C is the set of pilot subblocks in which the HRIS probes (see Def. 2), $\mathbf{\Theta}_P[l]$ is the probing configuration of the l -th subblock, as in (8), and $\hat{\mathbf{\Theta}}_R$ is the reflection configuration, as in (28). Following (7) and the above definitions, the BS receives the superimposed pilots at the l -th subblock, $\mathbf{Z}[l] \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times \tau_p}$, as:

$$\mathbf{Z}[l] = \sqrt{\rho} \begin{cases} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{h}_{p,i}[l] \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{p(i)}^\top + \mathbf{W}[l], & \text{if } l \in C \\ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{h}_{R,i} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{p(i)}^\top + \mathbf{W}[l], & \text{o/w,} \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

where $\mathbf{W}[l] \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times \tau_p}$ is the BS receiver noise whose i.i.d. entries follow $\mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_B^2)$ with σ_B^2 being the *BS noise power*; the noise is also i.i.d. over subblocks. In principle, the oblivious BS aims to estimate the stable reflecting equivalent channels $\{\mathbf{h}_{R,i}\}_{i \in \mathcal{K}}$ from the collected $\mathbf{Z}[l]$, for $l \in C$. However, this estimation process suffers from the probe distortion, which is now formally characterized by the summation of probing equivalent channels, $\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{h}_{p,i}[l]$.

Under the assumption of an oblivious BS, the BS carries out the following CHEST procedure. For the sake of argument, we focus on a single UE k that was assigned the t -th pilot, $p(k) = t$, for $t \in \mathcal{T}_p$ and $k \in \mathcal{K}$. Let $\mathbf{Z} = [\mathbf{Z}[1], \dots, \mathbf{Z}[L]] \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times L\tau_p}$ be the horizontally concatenated matrix of all pilot subblocks received by the BS. Denote as $\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{L_t} = [\boldsymbol{\Phi}_t; \dots; \boldsymbol{\Phi}_t] \in \mathbb{C}^{L\tau_p}$ the vector containing the t -th pilot repeated L times. The BS first takes the mean of the de-correlated received signals in (32), yielding in $\bar{\mathbf{z}}_k = \frac{1}{L} \mathbf{Z} \boldsymbol{\Phi}_{L_t}^*$ as

$$\bar{\mathbf{z}}_k \stackrel{(a)}{=} \sqrt{\rho} \tau_p \underbrace{\left(\frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^C \mathbf{h}_{p,k}[l] + (1 - \varpi) \mathbf{h}_{R,k} \right)}_{=\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k} + \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{w}_t[l], \quad (33)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_t[l] \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \tau_p \sigma_B^2 \mathbf{I}_M)$ is the equivalent receiver noise and $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k \in \mathbb{C}^M$ is defined as the *average equivalent channel*. In (a), we have used Def. 3 for ϖ as the relative probe duration. Below, we provide the least-squares (LS) estimate of $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k$.¹⁰

Corollary 3 (CHEST at the BS). *The LS estimate of the average equivalent channel $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k$ based on $\bar{\mathbf{z}}_k$ is $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k = (\sqrt{\rho} \tau_p)^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{z}}_k$ with $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k \sim \mathcal{CN}(\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k, \hat{\sigma}^2 \mathbf{I}_M)$, where $\hat{\sigma}^2 = \sigma_B^2 / (L\rho\tau_p)$ denotes the variance of the estimate.*

¹⁰To align with the channel-agnostic probing design, we assume that the BS has no prior knowledge of the channel statistics. Otherwise, Bayesian estimation methods [51] could be employed to enhance performance further.

Proof. The proof follows [51, p. 225]. \square

Measuring probe distortion: Thus, instead of estimating $\mathbf{h}_{R,i}$, the BS estimated $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k$. To evaluate the quality of this CSI and capture the impact of probe distortion, we define the following average NMSE:

$$\overline{\text{NMSE}}_{B,k}(\varpi) = \mathbb{E} \left\{ \frac{\|\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k - \mathbf{h}_{R,k}\|_2^2}{\|\mathbf{h}_{R,k}\|_2^2} \right\} = \frac{M\hat{\sigma}^2 + \|\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k - \mathbf{h}_{R,k}\|_2^2}{\|\mathbf{h}_{R,k}\|_2^2}, \quad (34)$$

which is a function of the relative probe duration ϖ (see Def. 3) and where the expectation was taken over noise realizations. Per (31) and Corollary 3, we rewrite (34) as

$$\overline{\text{NMSE}}_{B,k}(\varpi) = \frac{\frac{M}{L} \frac{\sigma_B^2}{\rho\tau_p} + \frac{\eta}{L^2} \left\| \mathbf{G} \left(\sum_{l=1}^C \mathbf{\Theta}_P[l] - C \hat{\mathbf{\Theta}}_R \right) \mathbf{r}_k \right\|_2^2}{\frac{\eta}{L^2} \left\| \mathbf{G} \hat{\mathbf{\Theta}}_R \mathbf{r}_k \right\|_2^2}, \quad (35)$$

where the first left-hand side term in the sum of the numerator accounts for the *true LS estimation error*, that is, if $\mathbf{h}_{R,k}$ was to be estimated without probe distortion, while the second term evaluates the effect of probe distortion. Observe that $\overline{\text{NMSE}}_{B,k}$ also captures implementation complexity since it depends on the HRIS hardware architectures; it also statistically varies over coherence blocks with factors such as the positions of UEs and channel realizations.

Remark 1. *From eq. (35), we can draw two main conclusions. First, there would be no probe distortion if: a) (obviously) the probe mode is not employed, i.e., $C = 0$ or $\varpi = 0$ or b) the probing configurations were identical to the reflection configuration, $\mathbf{\Theta}_P[l] = \hat{\mathbf{\Theta}}_R, \forall l \in C$. However, obtaining $\hat{\mathbf{\Theta}}_R$ before initiating the probing mode is infeasible, as it represents the primary objective of the probing process itself.¹¹ Second, the estimation error is maximized when the probe mode occupies the entire CHEST phase, i.e., $C = 1$ and $\varpi = 1$. From this discussion, an alternative way to measure the probe distortion is $\left\| \frac{1}{C} \sum_{l=1}^C \mathbf{\Theta}_P[l] - \hat{\mathbf{\Theta}}_R \right\|_F^2 / \|\hat{\mathbf{\Theta}}_R\|_F^2$, which measures how different the probing and reflection configurations are on average using a Frobenius norm. However, this metric does not capture the real impact of probe distortion on communication performance, which is addressed next.*

B. COMM Phase

During the COMM phase, the oblivious BS exploits the probe-distorted CSI in Corollary 3 to spatially separate the UEs while the HRIS is in the reflection mode. Let \mathbf{v}_k denote the receive combining vector for the k -th UE, which is a function of the probe-distorted CSI, $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k$, for $k \in \mathcal{K}$. Here, we focus on the specific case of the maximum-ratio (MR) scheme with $\mathbf{v}_k = \hat{\mathbf{h}}_k$ [21], as, due to space limitations, alternative choices cannot be thoroughly addressed. By focusing on a particular

¹¹Note that this reveals one potential approach to mitigate probe distortion: implement intelligent probing strategies using outdated location information as a guide, where again if the UEs were static and their channels as well (flat-fading), the HRIS could probe less frequently.

sample of the τ_u samples, the BS estimates a payload signal sent by the k -th UE as follows [21]:

$$\hat{s}_k = \mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{h}_{R,k} s_k + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}, i \neq k} \mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{h}_{R,i} s_i + \mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{o}, \quad (36)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_{R,k}$ is defined in (31), $s_j \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \rho)$ is a random data signal for j -th UE with $j \in \mathcal{K}$, and $\mathbf{o} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_B^2 \mathbf{I}_M)$ is the BS receiver noise.

We proceed by discussing the impact of the HRIS operation on communication performance more formally, motivated by the autonomous-RIS trade-off introduced in Section I-C. Let $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{P,k} = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L \mathbf{h}_{P,k}[l]$. From Corollary 3, we rewrite the probe-distorted CSI estimated at the BS as

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k \sim \mathcal{CN}(\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{P,k} + (1 - \varpi) \mathbf{h}_{R,k}, \hat{\sigma}^2 \mathbf{I}_M) \text{ for } k \in \mathcal{K}. \quad (37)$$

From this, we can see that the effect of the probe distortion is to shift the mean of the estimated CSI away from the reflecting equivalent channel, $\mathbf{h}_{R,k}$. Since the receive combining vector, \mathbf{v}_k , is a function of the estimated CSI, this shift will also inevitably influence it. Consequently, because of the linearity of the MR combiner, we can express \mathbf{v}_k as:

$$\mathbf{v}_k(\varpi) = \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{P,k} + (1 - \varpi) \mathbf{v}_{R,k}, \quad (38)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_k(\varpi)$ stresses that \mathbf{v}_k is a function of the relative probe duration ϖ (Def. 3) with $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{P,k}$ representing the part of the receive combining vector that is misled by the probe distortion and $\mathbf{v}_{R,k}$ being the desired part from the point of view of correctly spatially separating the UEs. Thus, the correspondent instantaneous UL signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) of (36) can be written as

$$\text{SINR}_k^{\text{UL}}(\varpi) = \frac{|\mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{h}_{R,k} s_k|^2}{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{K}, i \neq k} |\mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{h}_{R,i} s_i|^2 + |\mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{o}|^2} \quad (39)$$

and the instantaneous UL SE can be calculated as $\text{SE}_k^{\text{UL}}(\varpi) = \frac{\tau_u}{\tau_{\text{chest}} + \tau_u} \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_k^{\text{UL}})$, whose quantities inherent the dependence on ϖ from (38). We then apply the use-and-then-forget (UatF) bound to more accurately estimate the HRIS-assisted communication performance, as summarized below and adapted from [21, p. 302].

Corollary 4 (HRIS-assisted communication performance). *The UL SE of the k -th UE can be lower bounded on average w.r.t. signal/noise realizations as*

$$\underline{\text{SE}}_k^{\text{UL}}(\varpi) = \frac{\tau_u}{\tau_{\text{chest}} + \tau_u} \log_2 \left(1 + \underline{\text{SINR}}_k^{\text{UL}}(\varpi) \right), \text{ where} \quad (40)$$

$$\underline{\text{SINR}}_k^{\text{UL}}(\varpi) = \frac{\rho \mathbb{E} \left\{ |\mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{h}_{R,k}|^2 \right\}}{\rho \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^K \mathbb{E} \left\{ |\mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{h}_{R,i}|^2 \right\} + \mathbb{E} \left\{ |\mathbf{v}_k^H \mathbf{o}|^2 \right\}} \quad (41)$$

for $k \in \mathcal{K}$. Again, (ϖ) stresses the dependence on these quantities on the relative probe duration inherited from (38), acknowledging the effects of implementation complexity, which arise from the different hardware architectures, and of probe distortion, which arises from the probe-distorted CSI and is influenced by the specific hardware designs.

The above corollary summarizes the HRIS-assisted communication performance under implementation complexity and probe distortion. However, the impact of probe distortion remains sternly hidden. To gain further insights, we extend the analysis to examine how (38) influences the above result, aiming to demonstrate that probe distortion can ultimately reduce communication performance. While the impact manifests in the SINR, our focus shifts to the signal-to-interference ratio (SIR) for convenience. By applying (38) and leveraging the triangle inequality, the SIR of the k -th UE is given by

$$\underline{\text{SIR}}_k^{\text{UL}} \leq \frac{\mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{P,k}^H \mathbf{h}_{R,k} \right|^2 \right\} + (1 - \varpi)^2 \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \mathbf{v}_{R,k}^H \mathbf{h}_{R,k} \right|^2 \right\}}{\sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^K \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \bar{\mathbf{v}}_{P,k}^H \mathbf{h}_{R,i} \right|^2 \right\} + (1 - \varpi)^2 \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^K \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \mathbf{v}_{R,k}^H \mathbf{h}_{R,i} \right|^2 \right\}}. \quad (42)$$

In the ideal case of zero probe distortion, this SIR is:

$$\underline{\text{SIR}}_k^{\text{UL}} \leq \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \mathbf{v}_{R,k}^H \mathbf{h}_{R,k} \right|^2 \right\} / \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^K \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \mathbf{v}_{R,k}^H \mathbf{h}_{R,i} \right|^2 \right\}. \quad (43)$$

To show that the probe distortion can be *unfavorable*, that is, it *can reduce* the HRIS-assisted communication performance, we compare (42) to (43) and obtain the following result.

Corollary 5 (Unfavorable probe distortion). *The probe distortion can reduce the numerator of the SIR in (42) while simultaneously increasing its denominator. That is, probe distortion can elevate the interference power among UEs while decreasing their effective power; reducing, rather than increasing, the overall SIR, which is the primary motivation of deploying an HRIS. This effect is stochastic, as it depends on factors such as the positions of UEs, channel realizations, and implementation complexity (HRIS hardware architecture).*

Proof. The proof can be found in Appendix B. \square

The above result along with Corollaries 1 and 2 provide us ways to gain insights about the autonomous RIS trade-off and the underlying robust feasibility region. *Note that we focused on showing that probing distortion can be unfavorable to communication performance, but this does not rule out the possibility of the opposite.*

C. Non-Autonomous vs. Autonomous RISs

We briefly compare non-autonomous and autonomous RISs, informed by the operational insights discussed above. Regarding the complexity of the CHEST procedure at the BS, following end-to-end CHEST protocols, controlled RISs require the BS to estimate channel responses for all BS-RIS and RIS-UE channels to optimize the RIS configuration [7]. Without leveraging specific channel properties, such as channel sparsity, this involves estimating $K_{\max}(M+N+MN)$ channel responses (see [5] for details). Alternatively, for HRISs, the oblivious BS only needs to estimate $K_{\max}M$ channel responses, as indicated in Corollary 3, resulting in significant computational savings for the BS. In terms of overhead represented by τ_{chest} in Corollary 4, an HRIS requires the transmission of LK_{\max} pilot samples due to pilot repetition,

as detailed in Section IV-B. In contrast, a controlled RIS requires dedicated and explicit control to receive its reflection configuration from the BS, adding control overhead beyond that already needed for CSI acquisition [8]–[10]. To model this as simply yet comprehensively as possible, we consider that $\tau_{\text{chest}} = 2K_{\text{max}} + N + N/R$, where $2K_{\text{max}} + N$ represents the minimal number of pilot samples needed for end-to-end CHEST estimation, as specified in [5], and N/R models a basic yet unrealistic control channel capable of transmitting phase shifts with infinite precision and no errors at a rate $R > 0$, measured in phase shifts per sample, similar to the model in [8]. In the case of $R \rightarrow \infty$, we have *ideal control* with zero errors and overhead. In simple terms, the potential advantage of autonomous RIS over its non-autonomous counterpart lies in achieving $LK_{\text{max}} > 2K_{\text{max}} + N + N/R$ along with comparing the respective assisted communication performances. For large N , the first condition is readily met. In the next section, we demonstrate that gains can still be obtained even under less favorable conditions for autonomous RISs, specifically for N in the few dozens.

VII. EXPERIMENTS AND DISCUSSION

We numerically evaluate and discuss the fundamental trade-offs posed by autonomy, as defined in Section I-C.¹² Table I reports the simulation parameters used, motivated by a suburban setting that uses the HRIS to *extend coverage* to UEs in cell-edge conditions [2], [21]. The HRIS is located at the origin of a two-dimensional Cartesian system. The BS is placed at the second quadrant 1 km away from the HRIS at 135° . The UEs are randomly placed within a ring at the first quadrant with a respective inner and outer radius of 900 m and 1 km, representing a cell-edge condition. The BS receiver noise $\sigma_B^2 = -94$ dBm comprises the thermal noise over $B = 20$ MHz and a noise figure of 7 dB in the receiver hardware; whereas, the HRIS hardware has worse quality with a noise figure of 10 dB, yielding $\sigma_H^2 = -91$ dBm. The above choices ensure strong enough BS-UE channels, assuring their spatial separability.

A. Implementation Complexity Trade-Off

Probing performance: For this evaluation, we assume that each UE has a 50% probability of being scheduled within a given coherence block. Figure 7 shows the probing performance in terms of the probability of detection, P_D , for different choices of probabilities of false alarm, P_{FA} . We use Corollaries 1 and 2 to determine threshold values, and Monte Carlo simulations with 10^4 realizations to obtain the curves. Naturally, we observe degradation in P_D with a decrease in the power absorbed by the HRIS, $1 - \eta$, or a decrease in the relative probe duration, ϖ (see Def. 3). Furthermore, as expected, the DSP-enabled HRIS outperforms the PD-enabled counterpart; however, this performance gap narrows as $1 - \eta$ increases. Notably, we also note fluctuations in the performance of the PD-enabled HRIS, which arise from our design choice to alter the probing configuration codebook as a function of C or $\varpi = C/L$, as indicated in (9). Based on Fig. 7, we select

Fig. 7: Numerical comparison of the probing performance regarding implementation complexity for the PD- and DSP-enabled HRIS hardware architectures. We vary (a) the fraction of power absorbed by the HRIS, $1 - \eta$, and (b) the level of probe distortion via the relative probe duration, ϖ (Def. 3). We evaluate different choices of the probability of false alarm P_{FA} for $K = 4$ UEs with each having a probability of 50% to be scheduled on each realization.

Fig. 8: Qualitative comparison of the reflecting performance regarding implementation complexity for the (left) PD- and (right) DSP-enabled HRIS hardware architectures. We assume $K = 2$ always-scheduled UEs for $\eta = 0.999$, $P_{\text{FA}} = 10^{-2}$, $K_{\text{max}} = 4$, and $\varpi = 0.5$ or $C = 8$. To enhance visualization, the BS is placed 1 km from the normal line to the HRIS. The ‘ $\cdot \cdot \cdot$ ’ lines represent the 2 UEs positioned at (d_k, θ_k) : (10 m, 30°) and (20 m, 75°).

$\eta = 0.999$ and $P_{\text{FA}} = 10^{-2}$ for the next simulations, enabling us to focus on evaluating the reflection mode with a satisfactory probing performance, which is around $P_D = 93.14\%$ for the PD- and $P_D = 99.57\%$ for the DSP-enabled HRIS. Hence, when manufacturing the HRIS, the choice of the coupling parameter η can be aligned with the desired performance for both the probe and reflection modes.

Reflecting performance: To isolate the reflecting performance to not depend on scheduling, we consider $K = 2$ UEs that are *always* scheduled. Figure 8 shows the reflecting performance in terms of the HRIS-UE channel gain. Here, the selection of $C = 8$ indicates that the probe mode occupies half of the CHEST phase, $\varpi = 0.5$. As anticipated, the DSP-enabled HRIS demonstrates superior performance compared to its PD-enabled counterpart, as it is more effective in localizing the UEs and reflecting energy toward them, resulting in higher average channel gains. In terms of the NMSE_H , defined in (30), the PD- achieves 0.86 while 1.72×10^{-6} is achieved by the DSP-enabled HRIS, showing that DSP capabilities plays a huge difference in getting more accurate local CSI.

Overall HRIS performance: We now summarize the key findings regarding the trade-off under evaluation. Based on the complexity analysis in Section V-F, the PD-enabled HRIS requires 308 element-wise operations, while the DSP-enabled variant requires 3264 for $\eta = 0.999$, $P_{\text{FA}} = 10^{-2}$, and $\varpi = 0.5$. Hence, the PD-enabled HRIS could achieve a computational saving of approximately 90.56%, where likely similar gains are expected in capital costs and energy consumption (this very

¹²Simulation code is available online at [this link](#).

TABLE I: Simulation parameters.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Carrier frequency, f_c	28 GHz	Coupling parameter, η	0.999	Max. number of UEs, K_{\max}	4
BS pathloss, β_B	3.76	Receiver noise powers, σ_H^2, σ_B^2	-91, -94 dBm	Coherence block length, τ_c	128 samples
HRIS pathloss, β_H	2	UL transmit power, ρ	0 dBm	Number of pilots, τ_p	K_{\max}
Channel power gain, γ_0	1	Number of BS antennas, M	64	Number of pilot subblocks, L	16
NLoS relative powers, $\sigma_{DR}^2, \sigma_{RR}^2$	$90.8 \times 10^{-9}, 0.11 \times 10^{-6}$	Number of HRIS elements, N	32	Phase durations, $\tau_{\text{chest}}, \tau_{\text{comm}} = \tau_u$	64, 64

much depends on how the analog circuitry of the PD-enabled HRIS is implemented). Although the detection performance difference between the two architectures is only 6.43%, the DSP-enabled HRIS offers significantly higher quality in local CSI at the HRIS. In this part, however, we have focused on evaluating the operation modes in isolation. Next, we will assess a more practical scenario of interest that considers the impact of the HRIS operation on communication performance.

B. Autonomous RIS Trade-Off

Baselines: We consider three baselines. **Standalone** refers to an mMIMO system that operates independently, without the assistance of the HRIS. **Informed BS** represents an informed BS employing the stop-and-wait approach to avoid probe distortion while the HRIS is ideal with perfect probing and reflection performance. Also, we do not account for additional overhead needed for the BS to be aware of the HRIS operation. **Controlled RIS** denotes the non-autonomous RIS paradigm characterized by the control overhead outlined in Section VI-C, where $R \rightarrow \infty$ signifies ideal control while $R = 1$ indicates that one phase shift can be transmitted per sample with infinite precision and no errors. Also, we assume that the BS has perfect CSI. *Note:* It is important to recognize that the Informed BS and Controlled RIS serve as highly optimistic baselines and their comparison with HRIS-assisted performance is invariably unfair; but even so the latter show comparable performance while completely avoiding the need of dedicated, explicit control, as seen next.

Impact of the probe distortion under different levels of implementation complexity: Figure 9 shows the performance of an HRIS-assisted mMIMO system in terms of the quality of the probe-distorted CSI estimated at the BS, given in Corollary 3, and the SE, given in Corollary 4. To isolate the effect of probe distortion, we assume that the $K=4$ UEs are always scheduled. The level of probe distortion can be controlled by increasing the probe relative duration, ϖ (Def. 3). The higher ϖ , the better the HRIS probe performance, but the worse the quality of the CSI obtained at the BS. As expected, this is readily seen in the NMSE curves shown in Fig. 9 (left). From the SE curves, we observe that the Informed BS achieves 0.3254 bits/s/Hz/UE, while the highest SEs for the PD- and the DSP-enabled HRIS are 0.3251 and 0.3254 bits/s/Hz/UE, respectively, achieved at $\varpi = 0.625$ ($C = 10$) and $\varpi = 0.0625$ ($C = 1$). *The negligible performance gap demonstrates that keeping the BS oblivious of HRIS operations does not significantly impact network performance when the proposed orchestration framework is applied.*

Dual effect of probe distortion: As outlined in Section I, our goal is to highlight the effects of probe distortion and

explore its potential impact on HRIS-assisted communication performance. Figure 9 shows that, while probe distortion harms the quality of CSI acquisition at the BS, it only slightly influences SE performance. Specifically, even though the SE achieved by the DSP-enabled HRIS decreases when $\varpi > 0.5$, it never falls below the performance of the Standalone system. *This leads to the counterintuitive observation: in some cases, probe distortion may be favorable, that is, it can preserve or improve communication performance, even with the CSI quality at the BS deteriorating.* One possible explanation for this phenomenon is that probe distortion may introduce diversity among the UE channels without compromising their identity, thereby reducing interference. This is similar to the effect induced by spatial correlation [21] and channel rank enhancement [2]. Another explanation that supports the former is that we are analyzing a cell-edge condition, where CSI quality does not matter much as the received power is very low. Furthermore, probe distortion has a more significant impact on the DSP-enabled HRIS SE performance than on the PD-enabled HRIS, where SE is not affected by increases in ϖ . A possible explanation is that the PD-enabled HRIS produces a broader reflecting beam, distributing energy more evenly across the space; conversely, the DSP-enabled HRIS further narrows the energy focusing, leading to more prominent errors in CSI acquisition. *Interestingly, our results suggest that architectures and algorithms that depend on lower DSP capabilities can be advantageous in the presence of favorable probe distortion and in scenarios where CSI quality has a lower impact.* However, a more detailed understanding of this dual phenomenon of favorable and unfavorable probing distortion is required, as it is highly dependent on multiple factors, such as the HRIS hardware architecture, the receive combining scheme, and the deployment setting. From Fig. 9, the *robust feasibility region* can be visually characterized by finding values of ϖ in which the HRIS-related SE curves perform better than the Standalone baseline. For the cell-edge setting, the region is $\varpi \in [0.0625, 1]$, with gains up to 19.06% and 20.29% on average for the PD- and DSP-enabled HRISs, respectively. We report that this region eventually narrows as UEs are brought closer to the BS.

Autonomous-vs-non-autonomous RISs: By comparing the performance of the controlled RIS with that of the HRIS, we observe that the HRIS generally performs worse than the controlled RIS under ideal control conditions ($R \rightarrow \infty$). But, when accounting for control overhead, the HRIS can offer comparable or even superior performance depending on the value of R . Notably, this advantage comes with the benefit of not requiring dedicated, explicit control, which can be more costly than manufacturing and designing the HRIS itself.

Fig. 9: Performance of an HRIS-assisted mMIMO system with $K = 4$ always-scheduled UEs for $\eta = 0.999$ and $P_{FA} = 10^{-2}$. Adjusting the relative probe duration, ϖ , allows us to control probe distortion, with $\varpi = 1$ indicating maximum distortion. The two different hardware architectures characterize the two extremes of implementation complexity: PD- is the lowest while DSP- is the highest. For $\varpi = 0$, the HRIS-related curves have performance equal to that of the standalone mMIMO system, as this virtually means that the HRIS is turned off.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

We proposed a PHY-layer orchestration framework that aligns HRIS operation modes with mMIMO operation phases, enabling the study of fundamental trade-offs concerning two major challenges posed by RISs featuring autonomy: implementation complexity and probe distortion. As stringent conditions present in our analysis, we consider (a) two extremes of implementation complexity, realized by minimal HRIS operation designs over the PD- and DSP-enabled HRIS hardware architectures, and (b) an oblivious BS that fully embraces probe distortion. Regarding the implementation complexity trade-off, our results showed that the more complex DSP-enabled HRIS has clearly better local CSI quality, but the PD-enabled HRIS can counterintuitively outperform it in terms of communication performance due to *more favorable* probe distortion when supporting cell-edge UEs. Regarding the autonomous RIS trade-off, we observed that unfavorable probe distortion can degrade HRIS-assisted communication performance, potentially making autonomous RISs unfeasible if not properly designed. However, we also observed a *dual effect of probe distortion*, which can be favorable or unfavorable depending on several factors. Further research into the statistical properties of probe distortion is necessary to better understand this dual phenomenon. For example, we have conducted preliminary simulations that show that probe distortion can behave differently depending on the receive combining scheme being used; you can use our simulation platform to test it yourself for the zero-forcing (ZF) scheme.

In summary, we presented empirical evidence that an HRIS-assisted mMIMO system can outperform standalone mMIMO and controlled RIS systems even under stringent conditions. Future research can expand this analytical framework to scenarios where the HRIS supports multiple operators or BSs. Additionally, it could incorporate performance analysis of hybrid controlled/autonomous RISs, where some explicit control messages guide HRIS behavior in some coherence blocks while allowing autonomous operation in others.

APPENDIX A PROOF OF COROLLARY 1

Proof. We need to get the distributions of the numerator and the denominator of the left-hand side term of (14). We start with the denominator. For the null-hypothesis in (13) with

$A_k[c] = 0$, $\alpha_k[c] = |n_t[c]|^2$ is distributed as an exponential distribution. Specifically, $p(\alpha_t[c]; \mathcal{H}_0^{(k)}[c]) = \text{Exp}(1/(2N\sigma_H^2))$, where σ_H^2 is a known nuisance parameter. For the numerator, the signal under $\mathcal{H}_1^{(k)}$ is approximated as $\alpha_t[c] \approx |A_k[c]|^2 + |n_t[c]|^2$, motivated by analyzing the signal on expectation, resulting in $2\Re\{A_k[c]n_t[c]\}$ being 0 since the noise has zero mean. Note that its variance is still preserved in the term $|n_t[c]|^2$. This approximation will surely cause an overestimation of the performance since we ignore the cross-term mixing amplitude and noise. Another motivation for such an approximation is to note that the terms $|A_k[c]|^2$ and $|n_t[c]|^2$ would be higher in magnitude than $2\Re\{A_k[c]n_t[c]\}$, where for high SNR values $|A_k[c]|^2$ dominates; in contrast, $|n_t[c]|^2$ dominates in low SNR. Hence, the numerator of (14) is distributed as $1/(2N\sigma_H^2) \exp(-1/(2N\sigma_H^2)(\alpha - f_{LS}(A_k[c])))$. By the above and (14), the HRIS decides that the k -th UE is detected in the c -th pilot subblock if $\alpha_t[c] \geq 2N\sigma_H^2\epsilon_s = \epsilon'_s$. \square

APPENDIX B PROOF OF COROLLARY 5

Proof. Let the four terms that compose the SIR_k^{UL} in (42) be referred to as: $\text{SIR}_k^{\text{UL}} = (a + \varpi^2 b)/(c + \varpi^2 d)$. To support our claim that probing distorting can be detrimental, we need to show that $a \leq b$ while $c \geq d$ for arbitrary choices of $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{P,k}$, $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{R,k}$, $\mathbf{h}_{R,k}$, $\mathbf{h}_{R,i}$. We must work with at least $M \geq 2$. For the sake of argument, we choose $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{P,k} = [0, 1]^T$, $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_{R,k} = [1, 0]^T$, $\mathbf{h}_{R,k} = [0, 1]^T$, and $\mathbf{h}_{R,i} = [1, 0]^T$. This yields in $a = 0$, $b = 1$, $c = 1$, and $d = 0$. \square

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